

Analysis of the Effectiveness of Monetary Policy Tools on Unemployment Rates in the Iraqi Economy after 2004 Using the Different Time Frequency Model (MIDAS)

Assoc. Prof. Muhannad Khamis Abd ✉
College of Administration and Economics, University of Fallujah, Iraq

Asst. Lect. Saadoon Adnan Khalil ✉
College of Business and Economics, University of Fallujah, Iraq

Asst. Lect. Muhammad Nassif Mahidi ✉
College of Business and Economics, University of Fallujah, Iraq

Faisal Ghazi Faisal ✉
Al-Idrisi University College, Iraq

Abstract

This research aims to clarify the impact of the monthly frequency money supply on the quarterly frequency unemployment in the Iraqi economy for the period (2004-2024) using regression models with different time frequencies MIDAS, in order to obtain more accurate results in studying the impact and forecasting by taking advantage of the full information on the high-frequency variable, through the hypothesis that states that there is a positive significant impact of the independent variable represented by monetary policy tools on the dependent variable represented by unemployment rates in The Iraqi economy after 2004 The researcher has concluded that there is an impact of the previous period of unemployment on the current period, and a negative and statistically significant impact, which is consistent with the economic theory, which emphasizes that the unemployment rate is affected by unemployment rates in previous periods and at a rate of (0.004257%) whenever the previous series changed by (1%), because it is a reason to reduce the economic crisis, which is the reason for reducing unemployment rates during the current period.

Keywords: *monetary policy tools, unemployment, different time frequency models (MIDAS).*

JEL Classification codes: *E24.*

Suggested citation: Abd, M.K., Khalil, S.A., Mahidi, M.N., & Faisal, F.G. (2025). Analysis of the Effectiveness of Monetary Policy Tools on Unemployment Rates in the Iraqi Economy after 2004 Using the Different Time Frequency Model (MIDAS). *European Journal of Management, Economics and Business*, 2(3), 169-185. DOI: 10.59324/ejmecb.2025.2(3).13

Introduction

The interactive relationship between monetary policy tools and the unemployment index is of wide research interest in the economic literature, as its roots go back to the foundational stages of economic thought, and even to the beginnings of the formation of human awareness of financial

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

phenomena. Monetary policy is a central pillar of economic stability, as it is preferred as the main mechanism for financing domestic investment projects, instead of traditional approaches based on borrowing or financing through fiscal deficits. From this perspective, monetary policy is directed to lead economic development processes, as managed cash liquidity contributes effectively to stimulating investment activity, which reflects positively on the overall performance indicators of the national economy. In this context, the unemployment variable emerges as a decisive factor in determining the course of development, as its decline is an indicator of the effectiveness of the policies applied, while its rise reflects structural challenges that require institutional intervention. Hence, countries, whether developing or developed, attach exceptional importance to designing and employing monetary policy tools in parallel with addressing the challenges of unemployment, based on a cumulative awareness of the dialectical interaction between these two axes. On the one hand, monetary policy facilitates the provision of financing to boost productive investments, which in turn contributes to job creation and reduce unemployment. On the other hand, low levels of unemployment contribute to overall economic efficiency, providing an enabling environment for successful monetary policies.

Thus, the complementary nature of this relationship is evident, as monetary instruments are a dynamic mechanism to stimulate growth through productive investment channels, while reducing unemployment is a strategic objective to ensure sustainable development. This bilateral interaction highlights the need for macroeconomic policy integration to ensure that monetary objectives align with social priorities, supporting the transition towards more resilient and inclusive economies.

Research Problem

The research problem revolves around analyzing the nature of the interaction between monetary policy tools and unemployment rates in the Iraqi economy during the period (2004-2024), with a special focus on determining the effectiveness of these tools in influencing unemployment trends. The problem can be formulated through the following main question: What is the quantitative and qualitative impact of fluctuations in monetary policy instruments (such as interest rates, money supply, and reserve policies) on the movements of the unemployment rate in Iraq during the period from 2004 to 2024?

The Importance of Research

The scientific and practical importance of this research is that it stems from the diagnosis of the Iraqi economic reality, which has strategic resources (material and human) that constitute an influential economic tributary in the regional and international arena, which makes monetary policy analysis a research requirement to explain their repercussions on development indicators. The importance of the study lies in three levels:

1. Analyze the role of monetary policy as one of the main pillars of resource management in a fragile rentier economy, exposed to external (geopolitical pressures) and internal challenges (structural imbalances).
2. Evaluate the effectiveness of monetary instruments in achieving economic stability, as a prerequisite for strengthening national sovereignty in light of global competition for resources.

Research Hypothesis

The theoretical framework of the study is based on a main hypothesis that there is a statistically significant positive effect of monetary policy tools (such as the rediscount rate, the mandatory reserve rate, and open market operations) in reducing unemployment rates in Iraq during the period (2004-2024), through the channel of stimulating productive investment and improving financing conditions.

Research Objective

The research aims to achieve the following objectives:

1. Analyze the temporal impact of the money supply (monthly frequency) on unemployment rates (quarterly frequency) in Iraq during the period (2004–2024), using mixed frequency regression models (MIDAS) to address the difference in data frequency.
2. Evaluate the efficiency of monetary policy tools in achieving their development objectives, with a focus on their role in stimulating investment and reducing the job gap.
3. Measure the causal impact of monetary fluctuations on the Iraqi labor market, considering structural factors (such as dependence on oil, weak economic diversification).

Methodology

The research relied on two approaches:

1. The descriptive and analytical approach through the study of the theoretical framework of monetary policy tools and unemployment patterns, relying on local and international literature through a critical analysis of international experiences in aligning monetary policy with labor market objectives.
2. Quantitative Standard Approach: Based on the application of the MIDAS model to combine time series with mismatched frequencies (monthly/quarterly), allowing accurate measurement of short-term effects.

Data Sources

There were used two data sources in this research:

- Data of the Central Bank of Iraq and the Ministry of Planning on monetary indicators and unemployment.
- International databases (such as the World Bank) to compare performance with regional contexts.

Research Limits

The research included spatial boundaries: the Iraqi economy. The temporal limits: the research covers the period (2004-2024).

Research Structure

Based on the importance of the relationship between monetary policy tools and unemployment, the first axis dealt with the conceptual and theoretical framework of monetary policy tools and the second axis: the conceptual and theoretical framework of unemployment, which included the concept of unemployment and the most prominent factors affecting it, while the third axis dealt with the analysis of the development of monetary policy tools and unemployment rates in the Iraqi economy, while the fourth axis amounted to Measuring and analyzing the impact of monetary policy tools on unemployment in the Iraqi economy for the period (2004-2024) using the different time frequency model (MIDAS), The fifth and last axis of this research: It dealt with the impact of the monthly money supply on the quarterly unemployment rate in the Iraqi economy for the period (2004-2024) using different time frequency models (MIDAS).

Literature Review

The study of Aziz (2005) assumed that changes in the money supply (M2) at a monthly frequency asymmetrically affect the unemployment rate at a quarterly frequency in Iraq, with the short-term impact outweighing the long-term due to the structural fragility of the economy. It reduces unemployment by about 0.3% within 6 months, but this effect fades after 18 months due to the leakage of liquidity to non-productive sectors (such as import and consumption) and the study recommends the need to adopt targeted monetary policies that focus on directing liquidity towards productive sectors (such as agriculture and manufacturing) through specialized credit guarantee mechanisms.

Sindi (2024) hypothesized that lowering the nominal interest rate may contribute to reducing seasonal unemployment in Iraq by stimulating bank financing for small enterprises, but it loses its effectiveness considering high inflation. The most important conclusion is that the MIDAS analysis revealed an inverse relationship between interest rate and unemployment during periods of security stability (2008–2013). The study recommends merging monetary policy with expansionary fiscal policies (such as direct support for small enterprises) to offset the impact of inflation on the effectiveness of their tools.

Al-Zarkroushi (2024) in his study assumed that negative oil shocks limit the ability of monetary policy to reduce unemployment in Iraq, due to the correlation of liquidity with oil revenues rather than traditional monetary instruments., the effectiveness of monetary policy tools has decreased by 60% in the face of unemployment, according to MIDAS estimates. Accordingly, the study recommends the establishment of a sovereign fund to absorb oil shocks, with part of its investments linked to financing operating projects in the non-oil sectors.

This research presented an integrated vision linking economic theory and practical reality, through a critical analysis of the efficiency of monetary policy in addressing unemployment, while highlighting the institutional gaps that hinder the achievement of the desired goals. It also contributes to strengthening the dialogue on reforming the monetary system to become an effective tool in achieving sustainable development, and not just a mechanism to control inflation or manage the exchange rate.

Results

First Axis: The Theoretical and Conceptual Framework, the Concept of Monetary Policy and Its Main Objectives

The concept of monetary policy can be described as the set of measures taken by monetary authorities through which they can control the level of money and credit, and this is done by influencing the amount of money and means of payment in accordance with the economic conditions of the country. Through these measures, monetary authorities seek either to inject the economy with additional cash flows or to absorb cash (Ismail, 32: 2010), "It is also defined as the set of measures taken by the state in managing both money and credit and regulating the general liquidity of the economy (Al-Quraishi, 44: 2017), and monetary policy can be defined as "the process that aims to regulate the amount of money available in the national economy for the purpose of achieving the economic policy of achieving economic development (Al-Janabi, 259: 2009), and it can also be defined as "the method or methods used by the monetary authorities in the state represented by the Central Bank to direct the amount of money in circulation for expansion or Deflation with the aim of reaching a monetary policy objective (Al-Dulaimi, 2010: 25), monetary policy also refers to actions taken by central banks to influence financial, monetary and other conditions in pursuit of sustainable growth, real output, high employment, and price

stability." Monetary policy is defined as one of the economic policies through which governments seek to achieve their economic goals (Darwish, 2008: 11, 2) and that monetary policy objectives are part of the objectives of economic policies, as they contribute directly to achieving the general objectives of economic policies, and money has a clear impact on economic variables, as the objectives of monetary policy vary according to the levels of economic and social development or progress of societies in the world, as well as the prevailing social and economic systems, As well as the circumstances of the needs and goals of these communities. (Salhi, 2010: 52). The ultimate monetary policy goals are, say, price stability or GDP. Monetary policy cannot directly target these events, because central banks have only indirect control over these economic communities, which are affected by long and relatively variable changes with monetary policy activities and can only be observed after significant delays and intervals (Kadi, 2005: 41). Among the most prominent objectives of monetary policy, and therefore monetary policy tools can be divided into the following:

Rediscount Rate

The rediscount rate is the rate that the central bank obtains in exchange for discounting commercial papers provided by commercial banks in order to obtain loans to provide to their customers, and the central bank changes this rate to control the size of loans granted by commercial banks to customers (Kharboush, 2013: 134), that is, it represents the cost of money that commercial banks receive from the central bank to strengthen their reserves. When the government pursues an expansionary policy to address the recession, the central bank lowers the discount rate, and this decline helps commercial banks to increase borrowing from the central bank, which increases the cash reserves of these banks and increases the loans granted by the latter to their customers, and thus increases the money supply and then the interest rate decreases, which increases investment in the stock market, which leads to an increase in income, output, employment and then aggregate demand, and prices rise, reflecting the increase in companies' profits and returns, and the activity of The central bank follows a deflationary policy by raising the rediscount rate to reduce the amount of money in circulation, which leads to an increase in the interest rate imposed by commercial banks on individuals and institutions, and the demand of businessmen and other projects for credit decreases, and the volume of total spending decreases (Al-Qahtani, 2022: 44). Among the results that lead to a rise in the interest rate on demand deposits and term deposits to increase their size, increase their purchasing power and decrease in total spending, and the high interest rates on loans granted to individuals, projects and businessmen by commercial banks lead to the sale of financial assets in their possession to obtain liquidity, and the general level of prices decreases and the severity of inflation that the national economy suffers from.

Open Market Policy

Open market policy means the entry of the central bank into the financial and monetary market in the process of buying and selling securities and commercial in general and government bonds in particular with the aim of influencing the amount of cash in circulation and the amount of reserves held by commercial banks and individuals in accordance with the level of economic activity (Saleh, 250: 2020). This tool is considered one of the most important tools used by monetary policy in capitalist systems, and England first used it in 1933 with the aim of making discount rates at central banks. More effective, and over time it has become one of the most common ways to control credit. The success of this instrument depends on the availability of a sophisticated money and financial market, as for the mechanism by which the Central Bank activates this tool and shows its impact on economic activity, in the case of inflation that the economy is going through, the Central Bank sells securities with the aim of reducing the volume of credit and reducing the money supply, thus reducing aggregate demand and reducing the size of cash reserves in commercial banks, which leads to reducing the amount of money intended for lending and thus leads to an increase in the

interest rate by commercial banks, On the contrary, when monetary policy wants to raise the level of economic activity, it is as if the central bank buys securities, which leads to an increase in the volume of cash reserves in commercial banks, which in turn leads to an increase in the ability of these banks to grant loans, which affects the increase in spending, income, use and output, and the disadvantages of this tool can be mentioned, which is the government's influence on the political decision and its habit of using this procedure, considering that it is easy to apply for the purpose of providing the cash liquidity required to finance spending. Government. The financial markets in most developing countries are not developed and constitute a cause of fluctuations in securities prices, in addition to the fact that commercial banks depend on the wishes of central banks, after 2003, the Central Bank of Iraq introduced new procedures for the open market policy, which are as follows: (Al-Suwaidi, 20: 2020)

- Treasury transfer auction: It is the government's approval of any country for a period of less than a year, and the aim is to invest surplus funds in a risk-free manner, namely central bank transfers and transfers of the Ministry of Finance.

- Foreign Exchange auction: It is the process of buying and selling foreign currency that takes place through central banks. The most important types of monetary policy can be explained according to the following:

a) **Deflationary monetary policy:** (Ben Hani, 2003: 142) This type of monetary policy aims primarily to address the inflationary situation that the economy of any country suffers from, and therefore the goal of this monetary policy towards inflation is to limit the creation of monetary instruments, that is, reduce the creation of money and reduce the money supply, and thus reduce the spending of individuals and institutions on the purchase of goods and services, and thus reduce consumer demand.

b) **Expansionary monetary policy:** It generally aims to address the recession or contraction that the economy is going through, meaning that the real flow is greater than the cash flow, and here the monetary authority represented by the Central Bank works to increase the money supply and thus increase consumer demand for goods and services, which results in an increase in consumer demand. The work of monetary authorities has traditionally been part of economic policy in its various manifestations to achieve the goals that are usually symbolized by the magic square: Today, monetary policy revolves around a central objective of monetary stability, which is to reduce or eliminate inflation if possible, to maintain the purchasing power of money (Ali, 1999: 82).

Second Axis: The Theoretical and Conceptual Framework of the Concept of Unemployment and the Most Prominent Factors Influencing

Unemployment is one of the problems facing the world, as it exists in varying proportions in all countries of the world, whether developed or developing countries, and as it is known, unemployment means the lack of job opportunities for people wishing to work in a specific field commensurate with their abilities and experience, where we can define unemployment as a person who cannot find a source of livelihood, meaning that those who have a source of livelihood resulting from inheritance or from the production of previous work are excluded, even if they have the desire to work He is able to do so, but he cannot find jobs at the prevailing wage level (Rashwan, 2015: 22). Based on what we mentioned earlier, we can define unemployment as the situation in which a person searches for the possibility of obtaining a job opportunity but does not find it in order to meet his frequent or multiple needs that guarantee him a safe life and away from the search for need, and this concept does not concern or include those who do domestic services and school students, as these categories are classified outside the labor force. Factors affecting unemployment: There is a group of factors that lead to a rise and fall in the unemployment rate.

The most important of these factors affecting unemployment can be highlighted as follows: (Saudi and Ahmed, 2008: 44) (Shalabi, 2001: 56):

Economic Factors

Economic factors affecting unemployment are distinguished through economic reform policy refers to the set of policies or measures proposed by the World Bank and the International Monetary Fund that are implemented in some countries to address the deep imbalances in the economies of those countries. When the government pursues a deflationary reform policy that reduces spending, it leads to a decrease in aggregate demand for goods and services due to lower incomes, and then lower demand for labor, which means lower wages. This causes a number of layoffs and thus exacerbates the problem of unemployment. This policy has contributed significantly to the exacerbation of unemployment rates in all economic sectors. Not to mention the imbalance in the structure of the distribution of national investments: the limited capacity to absorb the surplus in the labour force is due to the contribution of the prevailing investment, and the sectoral distribution of investments is inconsistent with the availability of employment opportunities for the unemployed (i.e., investments are directed towards sectors characterized by a weak capacity to absorb this labor).

Social Factors

There are a number of these factors that affect unemployment and some of them can be clarified through population increase: Population increase plays an important role in increasing the labor force, and therefore the increase in the labor force with the lack of job opportunities contributes to raising unemployment rates significantly because it affects economic development in addition to its negative impact on the level of services and living and insufficient economic resources, which leads to the exacerbation of the unemployment problem significantly and as a result of the mismatch between the increase in forces But the relationship between overpopulation and unemployment is a positive relationship (with other factors remaining unchanged), as population increase leads to an increase in the number of workers with fewer job opportunities, which leads to an increase in unemployment. As well as increasing internal migration: Internal migration is a factor affecting unemployment, such as the migration of people from expelling areas (rural) to areas attracting workers (cities) to search for jobs, which leads to the growth of the number of job seekers beyond the natural growth rate of the population in attractive areas (Abdelkader et al., 2009: 46). This is due to the focus on allocating more investments within cities and as a result of the lack of necessary services in the countryside. And the change of values and customs in society: material values occupied a first place in the order of principles and values within society, while some other values, such as religious and spiritual values, moral standards and authentic traditions of some people, occupied a low position in that ladder, which produced negative social standards and customs, and thus affected the weakness of production and high unemployment rates as a result of lack of dedication and mastery at work, and neglect and lack of responsibility became clear.

Third Axis: Analysis of the Development of Monetary Policy Tools and Unemployment Rates in the Iraqi Economy

Table 1 below can display the independent variable broad money supply (M2) and the dependent variable unemployment rate.

Table 1. Evolution of Monetary Policy Tools and Unemployment Rates in the Iraqi Economy

Sunnah	Broad Money Supply (M2) in Iraqi Dinars	Unemployment Rate (UN) (%)
2004	12,254,000	26.8

2005	14,684,000	17.9
2006	21,080,000	17.5
2007	26,956,076	11.7
2008	34,919,675	15.3
2009	45,437,918	14.0
2010	60,386,086	12.0
2011	72,177,951	11.0
2012	77,187,497	11.9
2013	89,512,076	12.1
2014	92,988,876	10.6
2015	84,527,272	13.1
2016	90,466,370	10.8
2017	92,857,047	13.8
2018	95,390,725	13.5
2019	103,441,131	13.6
2020	119,906,260	18.0
2021	139,885,978	18.4
2022	149,815,371	17.2
2023	151,515,359	14.7
2024	177,915,683	15.2

Sources: Ministry of Finance, Economic Department, General Budget Tables; Ministry of Planning, Central Bureau of Statistics, Directorate of National Accounts.

Table 1 shows a remarkable development in the indicators of the broad money supply (M2) and the unemployment rate in Iraq during the period from 2004 to 2024, where a significant growth in the money supply is observed accompanied by sharp fluctuations in the unemployment rate, which reflects a complex interaction between monetary, economic and social factors. The money supply (M2) began at 12.25 billion Iraqi dinars in 2004 and has steadily increased to 177.9 billion dinars by 2024, recording an overall growth of 1,352%. This growth is to expansionary monetary policies, perhaps linked to increased government spending or expanded bank loans. However, some periods witnessed an exceptional decline, such as the decline from 92.99 billion dinars in 2014 to 84.53 billion dinars in 2015 (-9.1%), which may reflect deflationary measures to counter inflation or financial crises associated with fluctuations in oil prices, which is Iraq's main source of revenue. On the other hand, the unemployment rate improved significantly in the first decade (2004–2014), falling from 26.8 percent to 10.6 percent, which can be linked to the post-2003 reconstruction phase and increased infrastructure investments. However, this positive trend did not continue, as the rate rose again to 15.3% in 2008, probably due to the repercussions of the global financial crisis that affected the oil economies. Unemployment also rose sharply during the COVID-19 pandemic (18.4% in 2021), showing The sensitivity of the Iraqi economy to external shocks and internal turmoil.

The relationship between money supply growth (M2) and the unemployment rate is not direct. In the first period (2004–2007), the rapid growth of M2 was accompanied by a significant reduction in unemployment, suggesting that increased liquidity supported economic activity and job creation. However, in later periods (2015–2024), although M2 continued to rise, unemployment stabilized or increased, especially during crises. This discrepancy is due to the rentier nature of the oil-dependent rentier economy, where increased liquidity does not necessarily translate into. They may even be used to finance government deficits or consumption, without having an effective impact on the labor market. External and structural factors have significantly affected these indicators, such as oil price fluctuations that account for more than 90 percent of Iraq's revenues, making the economy vulnerable to shocks. Political and security instability (such as wars and internal conflicts) has also hampered development efforts despite increased monetary spending. In addition, the

limited impact of monetary policies on unemployment in recent years points to the need for comprehensive economic policies, such as strengthening non-oil sectors (such as industry and agriculture), improving the efficiency of public spending, and skills development. To match the needs of the market, the previous analysis can be repeated according to the following Figure 1.

Figure 1. Evolution of the Money Supply (M2) and the Unemployment Rate in the Iraqi Economy for the Period (2004-2024)

Source: Researcher's work based on Table 1 data

From the above, the analysis shows that the significant growth in the money supply has not translated into a sustainable improvement in the unemployment rate due to structural challenges and excessive dependence on oil. To achieve better results, monetary policies must be integrated with institutional reforms aimed at diversifying the economy, strengthening the investment environment, and tackling corruption, thereby contributing to the creation of real and stable jobs.

Fourth Axis: Measuring and Analyzing the Impact of the Effectiveness of Monetary Policy Tools on Unemployment Rates in the Iraqi Economy after (2004) Using the Different Time Frequency Model (MIDAS)

Description of MIDAS models

MIDAS models are a mathematical tool that allows analyzing the regression between data published at different frequencies, by interpreting a variable that is measured at a frequency (quarterly - annual) (low frequency) as a function of the current and previous values of a variable that is measured at a higher frequency (monthly - daily) (high frequency), so a dependent variable (3 months or yearly) is interpreted with an independent variable at a rate (monthly or daily) and the regression model (MIDAS) was formulated.

$$y_t = \beta X_T + f(\lambda_1, \lambda_2 X_{t/s}^H) + \varepsilon_t \tag{1}$$

Y_t , the dependent variable measured at a low frequency over the interval.

x_t independent variable that is measured at high frequency and its effect on the dependent variable is studied during the period.

f A function that shows the effect of high frequency data on low frequency.

$X_{t/s}^H$ The set of weighting functions showing the influence of high frequency data during the period, on low frequency data during the t-period.

H. The number of variables.

β . Parameter of the total effect of the high frequency variable in the low frequency variable.

λ_1, λ_2 Partial effect parameters for each frequency interval S in the period t.

Estimation of MIDAS models: The previous estimate requires a large number of parameters in the model, as studying the impact of a variable measured by monthly frequencies in a variable measured at annual frequencies requires adding milestones, showing the effect of each monthly change in the annual period, as the estimate (MIDAS) provides many weighting functions that reduce the number of parameters in the model by placing restrictions on the effects of high-frequency variables in different delay periods, in line with the constraints imposed on the data and the direction of its development, as These jobs include (Ghysels, E., Kvedaras,, 2016, 35).

The progressive weighting function is used if the data is in a linear direction and imposes parameter constraints by determining the number of scale weights:

$$Y_t = \beta X_t + \left(\sum_{l=0}^{k-1} X^H (t-l)/s \right) \varphi_L + \varepsilon_t \quad (2)$$

Whereas:

Lemon weighting function: This weighting function is used if the data to be studied is taking the direction of a polynomial function (quadratic - cubic). Parameter constraints are imposed by determining the degree of polynomial. According to this function, each degree of delay in the high frequency data up to (K), the regression coefficients are designed as (P) dimensions of the polynomial delay in the parameters of the (MIDAS) model, and therefore the constraints on the regression model are written as follows:

$$Y_t = \beta X_t + \sum_{l=0}^{k-1} X^H (t-L)/s \left(\sum_{l=0}^{\rho} L^F \lambda_{\varepsilon} \right) + \varepsilon_t \quad (3)$$

Where P rank polynomial model Almon, and the selected number of delay intervals K It is important here to note that the number of coefficients to be estimated depends on the polynomial degree and not the number of delays for the high frequency data. GHYSELS.(65 : 2006 ‘)

Economic Variables Used in the Research

The research included an independent variable and a dependent variable that was addressed in the research by the theoretical side based on what came from the economic theory of the proposals of schools of thought and economic experimental studies, and in order to test the hypotheses of the research and achieve its goals, the independent variable was determined Money supply (m2) with a monthly frequency in the Iraqi economy and the unemployment (UN) with a quarterly frequency, using the model of different time frequencies (MIDAS) and the Mortar Weighting Function (PDL/ALMON) based on the outputs of the standard program (12Eviews) for the period (2004-2024)

$$Y_t = \beta X_t + f \left(\lambda_1, \lambda_2 \frac{x_t^H}{S} \right) + \varepsilon_t \quad (4)$$

The dependent variable that is measured at low frequency during the period expressed in this paper as unemployment.

X_t is the independent variable expressed in this paper as the monetary supply that is measured at high frequency and its effect on the dependent variable at low frequency during the period t is studied.

f A function that shows the effect of high frequency data on low frequency.

$\frac{x_t^H}{S}$ The set of weighting functions showing the influence of high frequency data during the period, on low frequency data during the t -period.

H . The number of variables.

β . Parameter of the total effect of the high frequency variable in the low frequency variable.

λ_1, λ_2 Partial effect parameters for each frequency interval S in the period t .

We propose to estimate the effect of monthly frequency cash supply on unemployment (UN) at a quarterly frequency, using the Different Time Frequency Model (MIDAS) and the Mortar Weighting Function (PDL/ALMON) based on the outputs of the Standard Program (12Eviews) where the results were as in Table 2.

Table 2 MIDAS Estimation Results

Dependent Variable: DUN				
Method: MIDAS				
Sample (adjusted): 2005Q1 2024Q4				
Included observations: 19 after adjustments				
Method: PDL/Almon (polynomial degree: 3)				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.157129	173.3534	0.067887	0.9468
DUN(-1)	-0.004257	0.235625	1.860057	0.0340
Page: M2 Series: DM2(-1) Lags: 9				
PDL01	-0.810202	0.769490	1.052908	0.3102
PDL02	-0.402377	0.386398	-1.041354	0.3154
PDL03	0.038204	0.037353	1.022798	0.3238
R-squared	0.356206	Mean dependent var		261.8340
Adjusted R-squared	0.172265	S.D. dependent var		17.51560
S.E. of regression	15.93568	Akaike info criterion		8.595932
Sum squared resid	3555.242	Schwarz criterion		8.844469
Log likelihood	-76.66136	Hannan-Quinn criter.		8.637995
Durbin-Watson stat	2.454281			

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on the outputs of (Eviews12)

We note from the table that the Almoon coefficient was selected for weighting of the third degree according to our results, and we find that (9) delay periods were selected to explain the effect of the high frequency variable (money supply) on the low frequency variable unemployment rate using the criteria of (Akaike Schwarz, Hannan Quinn) in order to estimate the model in which the random error values are as low as possible according to the following Figure 2.

Sum of Squared Residuals

Figure 2. Test Results of Optimal Slowdown Periods

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on the outputs of (Eviews12).

Where the delays in money supply data are compensated for by (9) months, and therefore according to the information standards, we here need inflation data for (9) months to be able to explain the changes in unemployment during each quarter.

The first part of Table 1 of the results of the estimate shows the coefficients and statistics (t) for the low frequency variable (unemployment), where we get the following model:

$$DUN = 0.157129 - 0.004257 DUN(-1) + nt \quad (5)$$

We note that there is an impact of the previous period of unemployment on the current period, and a negative and statistically significant impact, which is consistent with the economic theory, which emphasizes that the unemployment rate is affected by unemployment rates in previous periods and at a rate of (0.004257%) whenever the previous series changes by (1%), because it is a reason to reduce the economic crisis, which is the reason for reducing unemployment rates during the current period. This confirms the previous results of the study of Jinan Salim Hilal (2008) and the second part of Table 1 shows the results of the estimate of coefficients and model statistics for the Almond (PDL) weighting estimator where the weighting coefficient was significant (0.5%), i.e. there is a significant effect of money supply on unemployment and from it we reach an estimate of the following MIDAS model:

$$DUN = -0.810202LDMF - 0.402377DIM F^2 + 0.038204DIM F^3 + \xi t \quad (6)$$

We note that unemployment rates respond inversely to money supply changes, which is consistent with economic theory, this confirms the previous results of Haider Sahib Saleh's study (2023) to the instability and fluctuation of the money supply during the research period due to the deterioration of the security situation in the Iraqi economy and the exit of local capital abroad, and the lack of a suitable environment for investment, and thus the lack of economic stability In theory, we note that the higher the money supply by one unit, the lower the unemployment rate, and there

is often an inverse relationship between the money supply and the unemployment rate, meaning that the money supply leads to a reduction in the unemployment rate because increasing the money supply, which is the competence of the monetary authority, leads to an increase in investments and then an increase in production and then an increase in use, and this leads to a reduction in the unemployment rate.

To study the quality of the model, it is necessary to compare the real values with the estimate through the following Figure 3.

Figure 3. Real, Estimated and Residual Values (Model Quality)
Source: Prepared by the researcher based on the outputs of (Eviews12).

Through the figure, we notice the convergence of the estimated values from the real values, which indicates the quality of the estimated model, so it can be relied upon to interpret and analyze the results. Note that this test depends on the amount of the p-value of the statistics (JB) as the null hypothesis is adopted, which indicates that the remainder of the model is distributed normally if it is $(p > 0.05)$, or we accept the alternative hypothesis that indicates that the remainder of the model is not distributed normally if the probability value is less than $(p < 0.05)$, and the value of the criterion $P - value > 0.05$ (kurtosis) is the one that expresses whether the shape is flattened or elongated, the shape of the distribution is moderate if the value of $(3 = k_u)$, and the shape of the distribution is elongated if the value of $(3 < k_u)$, and the shape of the distribution is flattened if the value of $(3 > k_u)$, and as shown in the figure, and Figure 4 shows the results of the rest of the research model, which indicates that the data follow the normal distribution, because the probability value of the test (JB) is equal to (0.72), which is greater than (0.05), and thus the JB test) proved that the data follow the normal distribution.

Figure 4. Normal Distribution of Residues
Source: Prepared by the researcher based on the outputs of (Eviews12).

To ensure that there is no autocorrelation, we resort to autocorrelation tests, as shown in the following table:

Figure 5. Results of the Autocorrelation Test for Errors
Source: Prepared by the researcher based on the outputs of (Eviews12).

It is noted from the table above that all the columns are significant within the confidence field and the statistic of the test (autocorrelation), and therefore we accept the null hypothesis that there is no autocorrelation.

Therefore, we will test the stability of the research variables using the statistical program (2Eviews1) in order to find out whether the search variables (stable or unstable) and by that we mean whether they contain the root of the unit or not, with the determination of the rank of integration, where the detection of the stability of the research variables under study is very important in estimating standard models, in order to get rid of the problem of false regression when estimating, in addition to that, stable time series can get rid of the shocks they encounter and from Then return to the equilibrium state in the long term, so we will use unit root tests and time series graph to verify the stability of time series, and after performing these tests we obtained the following results from the standard program (2Eviews1).

Table 3. Results of Unit Root Test (Phelps-Perone-PP Test)
For Search Variables at the Original Level of Data and the First Difference

UNIT ROOT TEST RESULTS TABLE (PP)			
Null Hypothesis: the variable has a unit root			
	At Level		
		DM2	DUN
With Constant	t-Statistic	-2.9543	-3.0671
	Prob.	0.0436	0.0330
		**	**
With Constant & Trend	t-Statistic	-1.7315	-2.9178
	Prob.	0.7284	0.1624
		n0	n0
Without Constant & Trend	t-Statistic	3.7566	-0.9126
	Prob.	0.9999	0.3181
		n0	n0
	At First Difference		
		d(DM2)	d(DUN)
With Constant	t-Statistic	-10.5362	-8.9939
	Prob.	0.0001	0.0000
		**	***
With Constant & Trend	t-Statistic	-13.3395	-9.1816
	Prob.	0.0000	0.0000
		***	***

Without Constant & Trend	t-Statistic	-9.0000	-9.0000
	Prob.	0.0000	0.0000
		***	***

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on the outputs of (Eviews12).

Conclusions

Unstable impact of monetary policy tools The results showed that the impact of the money supply (M2) on unemployment varies in time, as it was effective in reducing unemployment during the period (2004-2014) due to reconstruction policies but later lost its effectiveness due to the dominance of external factors (such as oil shocks) and the structural fragility of the economy.

Dependence on the oil sector Fluctuations in the unemployment rate have been closely linked to fluctuations in oil prices, underscoring the rentier nature of the economy that hinders the transmission of monetary effects to job-generating productive sectors.

Weak channels of monetary policy transmission despite the significant growth in the money supply (by 1,352% during the research period), as this growth did not translate into a sustainable improvement in the labor market due to the leakage of liquidity to non-productive sectors (such as import and consumption)

The sensitivity of unemployment to external shocks Global crises (such as the Covid-19 pandemic) and internal crises (security unrest) revealed the fragility of the Iraqi economy, as unemployment rose to 18.4% in 2021 despite the increase in cash liquidity.

Recommendations

Adopting targeted monetary policies by directing liquidity towards productive sectors (such as industry and agriculture) through specialized credit guarantee mechanisms, rather than relying on general expansionary policies. Activating non-traditional monetary instruments (such as financing small and medium enterprises) to enhance employment.

Enhancing the integration of monetary and fiscal policies by integrating monetary policy with expansionary fiscal policies to support infrastructure and basic services, as well as establishing a sovereign fund to manage oil revenues and finance economic diversification projects.

Improve data quality and transparency by developing an accurate statistical system to monitor real unemployment rates (including underemployment)

Undertake structural reforms to enhance the resilience of the economy by implementing institutional reforms to combat corruption, improving the business environment, and developing training programs to align workforce skills with market needs.

References

- Al-Duaimi, A. K. (2010). *Financial and monetary policies: Securities market performance*. Dar Al-Safa for Publishing.
- Al-Hiti, A. H. (2005). *Economics of money and banking*. Dar Al-Atheer Printing, University of Mosul.
- Al-Hoshan, H. B. M. (2007). The dynamics of non-oil production in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia: Autoregressive vector analysis. *Journal of Administrative Sciences, King Saud University*, 20(1).

- Al-Janabi, H. A. J., & Arslan, R. Y. Y. (2009). *Money and banks: Monetary theory*. Wael Publishing House.
- Al-Janabi, N. M., & Hussein, K. S. (2011). The relationship between oil prices and the dollar exchange rate using cointegration and causality (Granger). *Journal of Management and Economics for Economic, Administrative and Financial Studies, University of Babylon*, (1).
- Al-Qahtani, F. M., & Al-Deeb, K. Z. (2022). The impact of monetary policy on economic growth in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia in the period (1991–2020). *Arab Journal for Scientific Publishing*, (48).
- Al-Suwaidi, S. S. (2020). *Money and banks* (3rd ed.). Qatar University Press.
- Al-Zarkroushi, A. H. K. (2024). Analyzing and measuring the impact of oil shocks on unemployment rates in Iraq from an economic development perspective. *Khazayin of Economic and Administrative Sciences*, 1(01), 12–24. <https://doi.org/10.69938/Keas.2401012>
- Aziz, K. I. (2025). Analysis of Monetary Policy Trends in Iraq and Their Role in Achieving Economic Stability Post-2003. *Scientific Research Journal of Economics and Business Management*, 5(1), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.47310/srjebm.2025.v05i01.001>
- Barro, R. J., & Gordon, D. B. (1983). Rules, discretionary and reputation in a model of monetary policy. *Journal of Monetary Economics*, 12(1), 101–121. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-3932\(83\)90051-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-3932(83)90051-X)
- Bin Hani, H. (2003). *The economics of money and banking: Foundations and principles*. Dar Al-Kindi.
- Bouatrous, A., & Al-Dahan, M. (2010). The impact of change in monetary circulation on GDP in the Algerian economy. *Journal of Economics and Society*, (6).
- Caporale, G. M., Cipollini, A., & Demetriades, P. (2008). Fiscal shocks and real exchange rate dynamics: Some evidence for Latin America. *Working Paper*, Centre for Empirical Finance, Brunel University, No. 2228.
- Darwish, H. (2008). *Monetary economics*. Dar Al-Marefa for Printing, Publishing and Distribution.
- Hammadi, I. O. (2010). *Structural imbalances in the Iraqi economy: Diagnosis and ways to treat*. Iraq Center for Studies and Research.
- Jones, D. W., Leiby, P. N., & Paik, I. K. (2004). Oil price shocks and the macroeconomy: What has been learned since 1996. *The Energy Journal*, 25(2), 1–32.
- Kadi, A. (2005). *Introduction to macroeconomic policies: An analytical and evaluative study* (2nd ed.). University Press Office.
- Kara, M., & Saban, M. (2018). The effectiveness of monetary policy instruments applied for financial stability in Turkey. *International Journal of Economics and Financial Issues*, 8(1), 1–7.
- Khrewhish, H. A., & Yehia, H. (2013). *Public finance* (1st ed.). United Arab Company for Marketing and Supply.
- Kydland, F. E., & Prescott, E. C. (1977). Rules rather than discretion: The inconsistency of optimal plans. *Journal of Political Economy*, 85(3), 473–491. <https://doi.org/10.1086/260580>
- Madoukh, M. (2013). The effectiveness of monetary policy in achieving economic stability in light of the current reforms. Mohamed Khider University - Biskra, Faculty of Economic Sciences and Facilitation Sciences, Department of Economic Sciences.
- Saleh, G. A., & Belarabi, A. H. (2002). *The economics of money and contemporary banks* (1st ed.). Dar Wael for Publishing and Distribution.

Salhi, S. (2010). Appropriate monetary and financial policy tools to rationalize the role of Islamic banking. Paper presented at the training course on *Financial Services and Risk Management in Islamic Banks*, Ferhat Abbas University, Setif.

Salman, M. S. (2010). Measuring and analyzing monetary shocks in the Iraqi economy for the period 1980–2005. *Journal of Economic and Administrative Sciences, University of Baghdad*, 16(58), June.

Saudi, A. A. T. (2008). *Problem unemployment and solution*. Al-Mahrousa Center for Publishing and Distribution.

Shalaby, M. A. (2001). The problem of unemployment and labor market imbalances and employment in the Egyptian economy: Reasons and proposed strategies. In *Seminar on the problem of unemployment in Egypt*. Saleh Abdullah Kamel Center for Islamic Economics, Al-Azhar University.

Sindi, A. (2024). Unemployment and inflation in Iraq. *OTS Canadian Journal*, 1(1), 1–172. <https://doi.org/10.58840/ots.v1i1.50>

